

Research Article

The Synthesis of Methane from Chicken Droppings Using Locally Constructed Digester and Scrubber

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Abstract

The design, construction and testing of a bio-digester and a scrubber for the production of methane was done using locally sourced materials and chicken droppings. The structure of the digester consists of a very thick high density polyethylene flat cylindrical 2.0m³ tank. The volumes of the gas holder and water jacket were estimated to be 0.25m³ and 0.5m³ respectively. The chicken droppings produced biogas with high H₂S levels, which is corrosive and was removed when passed through a sponge of lead acetate in the scrubber and water in the water jacket. Investigation showed that 1m³ of biogas in a biogas engine can produce approximately 2.1kWh of electricity and 2.5 kWh of heat. This project identified and developed comprehensive route for the synthesis of methane with the view of informing the most cost effective and affordable technology which may open the frontier to people to harness, utilize and produce methane from chicken droppings through locally constructed digester and scrubber with optimal benefit to the low income earners in villages and cities for cooking and heating, and will not rely on the fossil methane that depletes each minute by the day and are never renewable. This digester was fed with 500 kg of chicken droppings and diluted with water at a ratio of 1:1. After one day a very small volume - 0.0001m³ of gas was observed, the volume increased to 0.00074m³ after two days and subsequently rose to 0.5835m³ after twenty days. The pH of the gas was stable and the temperature at which it was produced was within the mesophilic range. The production of methane from chicken droppings increases with increase in retention time. When tested using a 2-burner gas cooker, the flame produced was pure bluish, this is capable of producing a calorific value higher than that of fossil methane. The advantages of anaerobic digestion are numerous which include; generation of "green power", improved manure composition and less odor, no acidification of the soil as slurry has a pH of 8, higher availability of nutrients, giving higher crop yields, reduction in the emission of greenhouse gases and contribute to a sustainable agricultural sector. This is, therefore, envisaged for an alternative fuel for cooking, heating and generating electricity.

Key Words: Local digester/scrubber, chicken droppings, methane, hydrogen sulphide, carbon dioxide, slurry and sponge of lead acetate.

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Introduction

Environmental pollution is one of the serious problems that humanity and every living thing are facing at this age. Industrialization, economic growth and heavy conversion of natural resources are some of the reasons responsible for the global warming, acid rain and the destruction of the ozone layer (Thakur, 2006).

In the world, water pollution by heavy minerals from the mining and mineral processing plants, industrial activities, sewage drainages and disposal of agricultural wastes and access to energy resources gives rise to both human/environmental hazard and economic development. Therefore, the need for alternative renewable energy sources from locally available resources cannot be over emphasised. Abubakar, (1990) noted that over times, various sources of energy have been employed by man in order to solve his fundamental life problems. Man has used energy from water, plant and animals to obtain food, clothing and shelter, hence energy is said to be a primary tool for development. Developing countries like Nigeria get more challenges in terms of environmental protection because of their heavy dependency on fossil fuel. Daramola and Oyewola, (2011) reported that Nigeria is blessed with enormous conventional energy resources such as crude oil, tar sands, natural gas and coal as well as substantial quantities of renewable energy resources e.g. hydro, solar, wind and biomass.

Iwayemi, (2009) opined that the 2009 annual statistical bulletin of the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC) revealed that Nigerian proven/estimated crude oil reserves, natural gas, tar sands and coal reserve stand at 37.2 billion barrels, 5,292 trillion standard cubic meters, 639 million tons and 2.75 billion metric tons respectively. These fuel reserves are adequate to power a large part of Sub-Saharan Africa energy demand for many years, yet will eventually vanish.

The Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) reported that, as at 2006 a total of about 79.6% of households in Nigeria still depend on wood fuel for cooking. States like Adamawa, Nassarawa, Zamfara, Sokoto and the like has over 90% of their households depending on wood fuel for cooking (NBS, 2006). Ahmadu, (2009) said a sizeable number of urban and semi-urban dwellers use wood fuel while the majority of users of this fuel is in the rural settlement, which consists of between 60 and 75% of the population in Nigeria. With the recent high pump price of petroleum products in Nigeria, the dependence on wood fuel for domestic cooking and heating has astronomically increased. The key effort of research today is to discover the energy source which is environmentally friendly and ecologically balanced. But unfortunately the new alternative energy sources like the solar, hydro, wind, etc. need high economical investment and technical

power to operate, which seem to be very difficult for the developing countries like Nigeria. At present, biogas energy is seen to be the only reliable, easily available and economically feasible source of alternative and renewable energy which can be easily managed by locally available sources and simple technology for these rural villages and even towns. Their residues can equally be converted to liquid manure (slurry) for crop production.

A biogas plant is an appropriate and sustainable way to deal with human or animal wastes that definitely pollutes the environment. This system produces two extremely vital products from the wastes: biogas and slurry (liquid manure). Using biogas for cooking and lighting reduces the damage on the environment by decreasing the production of greenhouse gases, and the application of liquid manure on soil improves its natural fertility (Ocwieja, 2010).

More so, with the declining quantity of fossil fuels, it is critical today to focus on a sustainable and economically renewable and simple technology biogas production from the numerous biomasses available for future energy supply (Deublein and Steinhauser, 2008).

The contribution of a methane molecule (CH_4) to the greenhouse effect is about 21 times higher than that of a carbon dioxide molecule. Therefore burning methane, even though producing CO_2 , reduces its impact on the environment making it environmentally friendly (Biogas Digest, 1980). The bio-digesters are employed to treat municipal wastes, chicken droppings, cow dung, sheep and goat droppings to extract methane for cooking/heating, electricity and slurry for organic fertilizer (Alpha, 2013). The technology can be utilized to provide energy for households, rural communities, farms and industries.

Energy consumption in Nigeria has been increasing on a relatively high rate due to increase in population and scarce or high price of fossil fuel products. This is most evident in the persistent disequilibrium in the markets for electricity and petroleum products, especially kerosene, diesel and cooking gas. The dismal energy service provision has adversely affected living standards of the population and exacerbated income and energy poverty in an economy where the majority of the people live in poverty.

The total dependence on wood fuel as the source of energy for cooking has resulted in the devastation of the quality and quantity of forests and has posed a serious threat in maintaining ecological balance, thereby manifesting various problems like

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deforestation, flood, Global warming/climate change, soil erosion, landslides etc. Thus, an alternative energy source that would be affordable and environmentally friendly becomes necessary if the green forest must be preserved.

With the large number of poultry farms in Jos and its environs, producing tons of droppings everyday thereby emitting lots of methane gas when exposed to the atmosphere, which is greater than 300 times more harmful to human health and the environment than carbon dioxide.

Therefore, biogas technology could be an appropriate means for recycling this organic waste thereby achieving one of the goals the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of eradicating extreme poverty via waste to wealth initiative. It is for these reasons that researches like this one are desirable to chart a course for sustainable energy production and utilization while a cleaner and safer environment is enhanced.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

This research is aimed at the synthesis of biogas from chicken droppings for cooking and other uses which can be achieved through the following objectives:

- 1 To develop a process route for handling chicken droppings as a waste for the production of methane and liquid manure.
- 2 To introduce locally fabricated digester and a scrubber for the synthesis of methane
- 3 To test the heating effect of the biogas compared to the methane obtained from natural gas.

Literature Review

The fermentation process of chicken droppings leads to the breakdown of complex biodegradable organics in a three phase process: hydrolysis, acidogenesis and methanogenesis (Abbasi and Abbasi, 2012). In hydrolysis phase, exoenzymes (hydrolase) bacteria decompose-complex organic molecules (fats, cellulose, starch,) in waste into simple sugars, amino acids, and fatty acids. During acidogenesis phase, shorter carbon chains of volatile fatty acids (lactic, propionic, and valeric acids) are created by acidogenic bacteria, which are then digested by acetogenic (homoacetogenic) micro-organisms to produce acetic acid, carbon dioxide and hydrogen. In the final phase, methanogenesis, the methanogenic bacteria produce methane (biogas) from acetic acid, hydrogen and carbon dioxide, which typically contains 40-60% methane and 30-40% carbon dioxide (Rasi *et al.*, 2007).

The biological process of acidogenesis results in further breakdown of the remaining components by acidogenic (fermentative) bacteria. Here, volatile fatty acids are created, along with ammonia, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen sulphide, as well as other by-products (Hanreich *et al.*, 2011). The third stage of anaerobic digestion is acetogenesis. Here, simple molecules created through the acidogenesis phase are further digested by acetones to produce largely acetic acid, as well as carbon dioxide and hydrogen (Ferry, 1997). The equations below illustrate that various products, by-products and intermediate products that are formed in the digestion process of an anaerobic production of methane. The acids produced are processed by methanogenic bacteria to generate methane:

There are different industrial and domestic types of biodigesters which include: fixed-dome plants, floating-drum plants, balloon plants, horizontal plants, earth-pit plants and ferro-cement plants without scrubber. Of these, the two most familiar types in developing countries are the fixed-dome plants and the floating-drum plants (Werner *et al.*, 2012).

The first digestion plant was built in a leper colony in Bombay, India in 1859 using cow dung to take care of the energy needed to cook and light the colony (Meynell, 1976). In 1895, anaerobic digestion reached England when biogas was recovered from a sewage treatment facility and used to fuel street lamps in Exeter. The development of microbiology as a science led to research to identify anaerobic bacteria and the conditions that promote methane production (Meynell, 1976).

Denmark has been a world leader in anaerobic digestion development and implementation, especially for generating manure to electricity systems. One of the driving forces in Denmark is their goal of having 33% of their total energy produced derived from renewable energy sources by the year 2030. It is believed that the biogas production in Denmark would increase by a factor of 10 by the year 2020. In 2002, there

were more than 30 biogas plants that were operational in Denmark (Braun and Wellinger, 2002).

The United Kingdom (UK), has had government initiatives driving the anaerobic digestion and renewable energy industry. Notably, the “Climate Change Levy” and the “Renewable Obligation” are UK energy initiatives that are helping the development of anaerobic digestion. Although, the application of anaerobic digestion in the UK has not been as wide spread as other European countries. Regulations are driving the use of renewable energy and environmental beneficial technology like anaerobic digestion. One area of focus is the co-digestion of manure with animal bi-product wastes (Monnet, 2003).

Like the UK and other European countries, regulation is the impetus behind the adoption of this technology. Specifically, the ban on the land filling of organic wastes, phosphorus reduction regulations, and the Kyoto protocol requirements for Sweden has given anaerobic digestion an outlet for those waste streams to be handled and processed. Also, the inability to use animal by-products in feed in Sweden has made slaughterhouse and associated wastes available for anaerobic digestion. Manure is the primary feedstock for most of the biogas plants, so other waste streams co-digested are secondary substrates. A good example of a Swedish anaerobic digestion plant is the Kristiansand plant that processes a number of wastes. In 2002, about 2,000 agricultural plants were in operation in Germany, most of them using co-substrates (Braun and Wellinger, 2002). Although, Germany processes 8 million metric tons of bio-wastes, but 85% of those wastes are combusted rather than treated through anaerobic digestion. Most of the larger biogas plants in Germany use co-digestion of animal waste, human sewage, and food and processing wastes. Typically, a low solid waste stream is used for these types of plants. This is in contrast to Austria which has numerous biogas plants, but there is very little if any co-digestion taking place (Holm-Nielsen and Al-Saedi, 2001).

At present there are two major pathways of biogas utilization in Europe. The first example is from Sweden and Switzerland. In these countries the biogas is usually upgraded to more than 95% methane and then used as car fuel and to a lower extent fed into a gas grid as substitute to natural gas. In Austria, Denmark and especially in Germany the biogas is combusted in a combined heat and power facility (CHP) (Plöchl and Heiermann, 2006).

Biogas production from agricultural residues, industrial, and municipal wastes (water) does not compete for land, water and fertilizers with food crops like is the case with

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bio-ethanol and biodiesel production. In Africa the interest in biogas technology has been further stimulated by the promotion efforts of various international organizations and foreign aid agencies through their publications, meetings and visits. To date, some digesters have been installed in several sub-Saharan countries, utilizing a variety of waste such as from slaughterhouses, municipal wastes, industrial waste, animal droppings/dung and human excreta. Small scale biogas plants are located all over the continent but very few of them are operational (Tauseef *et al.*, 2013).

Table 2: African Countries with Biogas Producing Units

S/N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
Country	Botswana	Rwanda	Burundi	Egypt	Ethiopia	Ghana	Cote	Kenya	Lesotho	Malawi	Morocco	Nigeria	Rwanda	Senegal	Sudan	S/Afric	Swazila	Tanzani	Tunisia	Uganda	Zambia	Zimbabwe
Number of Small/Medium (100m ³)	Several	>20	>279	Several	Several	Several	Several	>500	400	-----	Few	Few	Several	>200	-----	Several	>1000	>40	Few	Few	>100	-----
Number of Large Digester (>100m ³)	1	-----	-	Few	>1	-----	1	-----	-----	1	-----	-----	F/S	-----	-----	Several	-----	1	-----	-----	-----	1

Source: Tauseef *et al.* (2013)

Materials and Methodology

The selection of all the materials was based on: cost-effectiveness, availability and durability. The following materials were used in this study: Sensorex EX20000R SpH meter, Brannan 830-T1 360°C thermometer, Black Horse 780.542.5292 plastic buckets, shovels, water-proof sacks, Normax JP64 Series funnel, Black Horse 780.542.5292 high density polyethylene tanks, tubes, fittings, plastic T-fittings and valves. Others include; 2-burner MAXI S3004FA-SF gas cooker, Vishnupriya Chemicals PVT L1-6080-56-4 sponge of lead acetate, cylindrical hollow metal, APT J-200 teflon band, Indiamart RTS20D steel saw, Marchants 50m/166ft measuring tape, LabMan MAB220 electric sensitive balance and water.

Methodology

This work was designed, constructed and tested at the department of Minerals and Petroleum Resources Engineering, Plateau State Polytechnic, Barkin-Ladi, Jos, Nigeria. A high density cylindrical polyethylene tank of volume 2.0 m³ was acquired from the market and made as the anaerobic digester. A hole was drilled on top of it where a 50mm diameter soft PVC pipe which carries the biogas to the scrubber was fixed. The mouth of the tank which has a lid was used to continually pour in the slurry (a mixture of chicken droppings and water) using a funnel, while a hole of about 50mm in diameter was drilled at the lower side and connected to a PVC pipe for discharge of slurry. A scrubber (either a cylindrical or rectangular hollow metal) of 100mm in diameter and 0.5m long was filled with a sponge of lead acetate. A flexible pipe of 50mm in diameter was fixed at the top of the scrubber extended it to another high density polyethylene with a volume 0.25m³. This polyethylene was inserted into yet another high density polyethylene with a volume of 0.5m³ containing water half filled. A pipe or hose was then connected on the 0.5m³, directed and fixed to a gas burner or storage cylinder.

The chicken droppings, which was collected from the poultry farm of the Plateau State Polytechnic, B/Ladi, Main Campus was treated by removing feathers, stones, soil, sticks and others. Five hundred (500) kilograms of this was diluted with water at a ratio of 1:1 and poured into the digester and covered. Digestion and fermentation took place where gas (mixture of methane, carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulphide) was produced. The biogas passed through the soft polyethylene pipe to a scrubber containing sponge of lead acetate which absorbed hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and carbon dioxide CO₂. Biogas from chicken droppings produces biogas with high H₂S levels (>2000 ppm). This is corrosive and needs to be removed. The biogas with possible amount of H₂S remaining passed through a pipe connected onto the outlet of the scrubber and goes to a gas holder (a smaller high density polyethylene) placed into a water jacket half filled with water which the gas holder floats in it. The biogas from the gas scrubber to the gas holder bubbled through the water where upgrading (removal of any remaining hydrogen sulphide and carbon dioxide) of the biogas was further made. The upgraded or cleaned biogas (methane, which is insoluble in water) was then channelled through a PVC pipe to a gas cooker where it burnt. The methane can be stored into a tank for later use. At the side lower part of the digester, where the pipe of 50mm and valve was fixed, decomposed slurry was removed and taken as liquid manure.

The tank was clearly placed above the ground level and outside the shed where it was exposed to the sunlight for heating and fermentation of droppings enhanced.

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Design Considerations

(i) **Digester Operating Volume:** The operating volume of the digester is simply the volume of slurry in the digester. The operating volume of the digester (V_o) was determined on the basis of the chosen retention time (RT) and the daily droppings input quantity (S_d), and was given as: $V_o = S_d RT$ [m³/day]

Where: V_o = operating volume of the digester

S_d = amount of the chicken droppings and water (in most cases ratio 1:1)

RT = retention time (the interval of time during which the biomass is allowed to decompose in the digester).

(ii) **Total Volume:** The total volume of the digester (V_T) should be greater than the operating volume in order to give room for the biogas produced and the rise of the slurry during fermentation. The operating volume of the digester must not be beyond 90% of the total volume of the digester. The total volume was therefore given as: $V_T = \frac{V_o}{0.8}$

(iii) **Digester dimension:** Having determined the total volume of the digester, a ratio for the dimensions can be adopted, depending on the chosen geometric shape of the digester. For a cylindrical digester, the chosen geometry for this project: $V_T = \pi r_d^2 h_d$

Where V_T = Total volume of digester

r_d = radius of digester

h_d = height of digester

(iv) **Digester Temperature:** The digester is designed to operate within the mesophilic temperature range (20 - 40°C), this can be achieved by natural heating from the sun. An absorptive surface is required for the digester if needed; this is to absorb solar radiation during the day time. An insulating material is required for the digester at night, this is to retain the heat within the digester and keep temperature fluctuations within manageable limits. Otherwise, the digester can produce methane that can be used for two days without insulation.

(a) **Volume of the Gas Holder (V_g):** The gas holder volume (V_g) depends on the relative rates of gas generation, gas consumption and the geometric shape of the digester. A safety margin of between 10 - 20% is always allowed. For a cylindrical gas holder:

$$V_g = \pi r_g^2 h_g$$

Where, V_g = volume of gas holder
 r_g = radius of gas holder
 h_g = height of gas holder

- (b) **Water Jacket:** The water jacket holds the water in which the gas holder floats. It was of the same geometrical shape as the gas holder. The radius was a little larger than that of the gas holder to give clearance for sliding of the gas holder:

$$R_j = r_g + c$$

Where, R_j = radius of water jacket
 r_g = radius of gas holder
 c = clearance

The height of the water jacket was higher than the height of the gas holder, therefore:

$$h_j > h_g$$

Where: h_j = height of water jacket
 h_g = height of gas holder

Volume of water jacket (V_j) is given as: $V_j = \pi r_j^2 h_j$

Where: r_j = radius of water jacket
 h_j = height of water jacket

Guide Frame:

The guide frame is to guide the gas holder in its upward displacement and prevent it from tilting. It's also to provide a maximum displacement position for the gas holder. Two rods were mounted on the opposite sides of the gas holder, sliding through corresponding slides ways on the water jacket.

Force on Gas Holder (F_g):

The force on the gas holder is given as: $F_g = P_g \times A_g$

Where: P_g = Pressure in gas holder

A_g = Cross-sectional area of gas holder

Evaluation of the Performance of The Digester

The evaluation of the technical performance of the anaerobic digestion process was carried out with respect to the gas production and the treatment efficiency of each of the

digester systems. The reactor was monitored for the 20-day retention time in the following areas.

- (i) Measurement of gas production,
- (ii) Analysis of feedstock and effluent to evaluate the treatment efficiency of the digestion process.

Measurement of Gas Production from the Digested Chicken Droppings

The gas holder was calibrated with the aid of a rule which enabled the reading of the daily gas production of the substrate in the anaerobic digester.

The biogas produced was measured each day and taken as the total gas content of the gas holder. The produced biogas was also measured by computing the volume of the gas holder floating over water level in the water jacket on a daily basis. The gas holder (cylinder) had a base diameter of 0.27m.

$$\text{The base area, } A = \pi \frac{d^2}{4} = \frac{\pi \times (1.5)^2}{4}$$

The height of the gas holder above water level was read off on the rule attached to the gas holder for calibration. Height (h) = x , which varies.

The volume of biogas at atmospheric pressure was then obtained as the volume of cylinder above water level, given by: Volume, (V) = $\pi \frac{d^2 h}{4} = Ah$ where $h = x$

Substituting for A from above, V varied.

where V = volume of biogas,

x = height of cylinder above water level.

Daily Monitoring of Operational Parameters

In order to study and determine the most feasible local environmental conditions to optimally operate the developed biogas facilities, various physical and chemical parameters were monitored to check the status of the digester. Monitoring of the plant was carried out every day between 0700 and 1900 hours. Readings of values of digester, ambient temperatures and pH were taken. Below are the physico-chemical parameters that were monitored.

Temperature: This gives the kinetic energy of atoms or molecules. It was measured and determined the feedstock influence on the temperature and consequently, the metabolism of the bacteria. Thermometers were used and measured the temperature of

the digester three times daily and that of the main campus of the Plateau State Polytechnic, B/Ladi was recorded at 1200hrs daily.

pH: This gives the intensity of acidic or basic character at a given temperature. It was measured and determined the feedstock influence on the acidity/alkalinity and consequently, the metabolism of the bacteria. Samples were measured at ambient temperature with a pH meter.

Domestic Cooking With Produced Gas

The performance evaluation of the gas produced from the chicken droppings digested was carried out by boiling water using a gas stove. The gas colour which tells the cooking rate (Cr) and the biogas consumption rate (Q) were determined.

Results

A total of 500kg of chicken droppings was diluted with water and slurry produced. The pH of the gas was measured to be slightly acidic but became neutral afterwards. This progressive increase and stabilization in pH could account for steady rate of gas production which is in agreement with the studies carried out previously by Ahmadu (2009). The temperature inside the digester was stable fluctuating between 32 and 36°C which is within the mesophilic range. The gas holder had a base diameter of 1.5m giving an area of 1.767m². The volume of gas inside the gas holder on the first day of digestion was very small - 0.0001m³, on the second day it increased to 0.00074m³ and subsequently it reached up to 0.5835m³ after 20 days of digestion. This means the more retention time of digestion the higher the volume of methane is produced. This methane was tested using a gas cooker; a very clear bluish flame emerged.

Ahmadu, T. O. (2009) compared the synthesis of methane from cow dung and chicken droppings while Alfa, M. I. (2013) compared the production of methane from cow dung, chicken droppings and lemon grass. Both used slake lime and water for the upgrading or scrubbing of the methane and reported that there could be some traces of hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). But in this study, a sponge of lead acetate and water were used for the removal of H₂S and CO₂. From the pure bluish colour of the flame, it showed there was no left over of H₂S and CO₂ in the gas.

References

Abbasi, T. and Abbasi, S. A. (2012). Is the Use of Renewable Energy Sources an Answer to the Problems of Global Warming and Pollution? *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 42, 99-154.

Abubakar, M. M. (1990). Biogas Generation from Animal Wastes. *Nigerian Journal of Renewable Energy*. 1: 69-73.

Ahmadu T. O. (2009). Comparative Performance of Cow Dung and Chicken Droppings for Biogas Production. A Master of Science Thesis, submitted to the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Pp 96 -100.

Alfa, M.I. (2013). Comparative Study of Biogas Production from Cow Dung, Chicken Droppings and *Cymbopogon citratus* as an Alternative Energy Sources in Nigeria. A M. Sc Thesis submitted to the department of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Pp 102 -104

Biogas Digest (1980). Information and Advisory Service on Appropriate Technology (Isat) Biogas Basic (gtz) vol. 1, Pp 201-207.

Braun, R. and Wellinger, A. (2002). Biogas Production - Potential of Co-digestion. Institute of Agrobiotechnology. Department of Environmental Biotechnology, Lorenz Strasse. Buswell, A.M.; Hatfield.

Daramola, M. S. and Oyewola, O. M. (2011). Wind Speed Distribution and Characteristics in Nigeria. *ARNP Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, Vol. 6, No. 2. Available

http://www.arpnjournals.com/jeas/research_papers/rp_2011/jeas_0211_458.pdf.

Retrieved (21/09/2011)

Deublein, K and Steinhauser, E. (2008). Biogas from Waste and Renewable Resources; An Introduction. Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co KGaA. Weiheim.

Ferry, W. D. (1997). Anaerobic Fermentations. Urbana, IL: State of Illinois. Department of Registration and Education, Characteristics in Nigeria. Bulletin 32 *ARNP Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, Vol. 6, Conference, Istanbul, Turkey, available on Delhi; Ik International Pvt Ltd.

Hanreich, A., Schimpf, U., Zakrzewski, M., Schlüter, A., Bendorf, D. and Klocke, M. (2011). Monitoring of Changes within a Microbial, Biogas Producing Community. In Proceedings of the First International Conference on Biogas Microbiology: Leipzig. Edited by Kleinstüber, S. and Nikolausz, M. UFZ Press, Leipzig; 2011:49. Ferry J.G. Enzymology of the Fermentation of Acetate to Methane by Methanosarcinathermophila. *Biofactors*, 6:25-35.

Holm-Nielsen, J. B. and Al-Saedi T. (2001). Biogas in Europe - A General overview. <http://www.ecop.ucl.ac.be/aebiom/articles/biogas/biogas.htm>, accessed 9/6/2015

Iwayemi, A. (2009). Nigeria's Dual Energy Problems: Policy Issues and Challenges being a Paper Presented at the 31st International Association for Energy Economics International Conference, Istanbul, Turkey, available on www.iaee.org/en/publications/newsletterdl.aspx?id=53

Meynell, P. J. (1976). Methane: Planning a Digester. New York: Schocken Books. Pp 3.

Monnet, F. (2003). An Introduction to Anaerobic Digestion of Organic Wastes. Remande, Scotland.

Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (2006). Social Statistics in Nigeria Available on No. 2. Available http://www.arnjournals.com/jeas/research_papers.

Ocwieja, S. M. (2010). Life Cycle Thinking Assessment Applied to Three Biogas Projects in Central Uganda. Michigan Technological University, available at <http://www.cee.mtu.edu/peacecorps/studentfiles/Ocwieja-Uganda.pdf>. Retrieved on (17/5/2011).

Plöchl, M. and Heiermann, M. (2006). Biogas Farming in Central and Northern Europe: A Strategy for Developing Countries. Agricultural Engineering International: *The CIGRE Journal*

Rasi, S., Veijanen, A. and Rintala, J. (2007). Trace Compounds of Biogas from Different Biogas Production Plants. *Energy*, 1375-1380

Tauseef, S. M., Premalatha, M., Abbasi, T. and Abbasi, S. A. (2013). Methane Capture from Livestock Manure. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 117, 187-207.

Thakur, I. S. (2006). Environmental Biotechnology: Basic Concept and Applications. Michigan Technological University, available at <http://www.cee.mtu.edu/peacecorps/studentfiles/Ocwieja>

Werner, K., Uta, P., Stefan, H., Klingler, B. and Kellner, C. (2012). *Biogas Digest*. Volume II, Pp 8 www.iaee.org/en/publications/newsletterdl.aspx?id=53.